

Effective, Fair and Inclusive Climate Policies in Europe and in the Global South

Challenges and way forward

September 2025

Funded by European Union's Horizon
Europe Programme under Grant
Agreement No. 101094551

Key messages

- **Ambitious European climate policies play an important role** in tackling global warming, driving rapid emission reductions while setting international benchmarks that influence partners and multilateral cooperation.
- **ETS 2 and CBAM mark a new phase in European climate governance, extending carbon pricing.** Their success will depend on their ability to embrace social fairness and international equity. Without robust redistribution at home and solidarity abroad, these measures risk undermining the EU's climate ambitions.
- **The Social Climate Fund**, if expanded in fundings and scope, and transparently managed, can provide both short-term support and long-term investment, helping vulnerable households cope with rising energy costs while participating in the low-carbon transition.
- **CBAM can enhance fairness and legitimacy** when implemented inclusively, through support for SMEs, and the recycling of revenues into climate programmes in low-income countries especially affected by negative effects of climate change.

Background & Context

The European Union (EU) has consistently presented itself as a global leader in climate governance, committing to reach climate neutrality by 2050 first through the European Green Deal and subsequent policy package Fit for 55, and now through the 2040 Climate Target. At the heart of its climate strategy lies the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), launched in 2005 as one of the world's largest carbon markets. The ETS employs a cap-and-trade system to limit emissions while permitting allowances to be traded, thus creating an incentive for industries to decarbonise at the lowest possible cost. The system is likely to have contributed to a 47% reduction in emissions for the covered sectors and now aims for a 62% cut of GHG by 2030 compared with 2005 levels. Reforms to the EU ETS introduced by the Fit for 55 package also envisage a gradual phase-out of free allowances, the inclusion of new sectors such as shipping, and the increased use of revenues to support innovation and modernisation funds. Despite these achievements, the ETS has so far focused mainly on large industrial emitters and the power sector, leaving out significant parts of the economy.

To fill this gap, the EU is establishing a parallel

system, ETS 2, expected to begin in 2027. This new carbon market will cover emissions from road transport, buildings, and small businesses not already covered by ETS, as well as sectors with high climate impact but historically left outside emissions trading. ETS 2 is critical for decarbonising everyday consumption but poses challenges of fairness as it will have a direct impact on people. Rising fuel and heating costs hit lower-income households hardest, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe, where energy poverty is already critical. In recognition of these risks, the EU has created the Social Climate Fund, designed to channel part of the revenues from ETS 2 into measures that protect vulnerable households and small businesses. Yet questions remain about the adequacy of its budget, insufficient targeting of the fund to adequately support vulnerable households, and its ability to deliver both short-term relief and long-term structural change.

Parallel to its domestic climate efforts, the EU also faces the challenge of carbon leakage, which is the relocation of carbon-intensive industries to jurisdictions with weaker climate policies outside the EU. This undermines global emissions reductions and

threatens European competitiveness.

To address this, the EU has introduced the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which levies a carbon price on imports in highly emission-intensive sectors such as steel, aluminium, cement, fertilisers, electricity, and hydrogen.

CBAM entered a transitional reporting phase in October 2023, with full implementation planned for 2026. During this period, importers must report the embedded emissions of covered products, and from 2026 onwards they will be required to purchase CBAM certificates at prices linked to EU ETS allowances. Thus, CBAM is designed to ensure a level playing field for EU industries and to encourage trading partners to adopt their own carbon pricing schemes. However, while it has been hailed as a landmark policy in aligning trade with climate goals, it has also raised political, legal, and diplomatic concerns. First, CBAM is expected to affect European firms that rely heavily on imports from sectors covered by the mechanism. For these companies, higher import costs could translate into reduced competitiveness, particularly in manufacturing and construction industries where low-cost inputs are critical. Second, the impact of CBAM on EU trading partners,

particularly in the Global South, is another source of concern. Research indicates that while macroeconomic effects may be modest, the policy could generate significant distributional impacts. This suggests that CBAM, if not carefully managed, could deepen inequality within exporting countries and worsen poverty and food insecurity.

Some scholars criticise it as an extraterritorial measure that effectively forces third countries to adopt EU-like carbon standards, potentially infringing on sovereignty. The EU, however, maintains that CBAM is WTO-compliant, pointing to Article XX of General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), which allows trade measures necessary to protect health or natural resources. Other scholars argue that applying CBAM uniformly across all trading partners violates the principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities (CBDR-RC), which underpins international climate agreements. Nevertheless, CBAM is already influencing policy globally. Countries such as Turkey and Brazil have accelerated discussions on domestic carbon markets to protect their exporters' access to the EU. This demonstrates CBAM's potential to stimulate climate ambition abroad.

SPES Evidence

The available evidence highlights both the environmental effectiveness and the socio-economic challenges of ETS 2 and CBAM. Together, they represent powerful tools for cutting emissions and strengthening Europe's climate leadership, but without careful design and decisive revenue recycling, their distributional consequences risk undermining support for the transition.

Distributional impacts of ETS 2 within Europe

The reviewed studies in Cammeo et al. (2024) show that extending carbon pricing to transport and heating will hit lower-income households hardest, since they spend a greater share of their income on energy and mobility. In France, projected household losses range from €323 to €510 annually, but redistributing auction revenues could offset these costs for the poorest 30 percent of families. In Italy, annual welfare losses may exceed €170 per person, with food and energy prices particularly burdensome for vulnerable households. In Hungary, the poorest decile faces welfare losses 1.6 times greater than the richest, while energy prices could rise by over 30 percent. These findings underline the importance of the Social Climate Fund

and targeted compensation to prevent ETS 2 from worsening inequality. Evidence also shows that people across Europe are more supportive of carbon pricing when revenues are visibly invested in clean energy, public transport, or direct household support, rather than left unallocated.

Uneven impacts of CBAM across countries and sectors

The European Commission's impact assessment suggests CBAM will modestly cut GDP by 0.2 percent and consumption by 0.5 percent, while spurring investment in clean technologies. It is also expected to reduce carbon leakage by nearly 30 % by 2030, a crucial step in fostering the effectiveness of EU climate policies. However, Cammeo et al. (2025) shows that exposure to CBAM varies sharply across Europe. Countries such as Bulgaria, Greece, and Italy, with high reliance on steel and aluminium imports, face greater risks of rising costs and competitiveness losses, especially in construction and manufacturing. In contrast, France and Luxembourg are less exposed, reflecting their respective industrial structures. Small and medium-sized enterprises across Europe also face disproportionate compliance

ETS 2 and CBAM represent powerful tools for cutting emissions and strengthening Europe's climate leadership but without careful design their distributional consequences risk undermining support for the transition.

costs, as many lack the resources to trace and verify carbon content in supply chains. Internationally, CBAM has already influenced countries like Turkey, Brazil, and Malaysia to accelerate carbon market reforms. But it also raises concerns about fairness, as uniform application may penalise developing economies dependent on exports to Europe, challenging the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities in climate action.

Impact of CBAM on third countries

The effects of CBAM are particularly significant for the EU's trading partners in the Global South, which are more vulnerable to international economic and geopolitical shocks. Davalos et al. (2025) and Salisu et al. (2025) highlight that CBAM could harm these economies by reducing exports to the EU, or through supply-side effects, if trade tensions escalate and disrupt global supply chains. Simulations of the policy's impact on EU import prices suggest that productivity and competitiveness would decline in many low- and middle-income countries, even if inflationary effects remain limited. Country-level studies give further insights into these risks. In Egypt, for example, CBAM has only

a modest impact on the economy overall because carbon-intensive exports represent a small share of total trade. However, household-level impacts are severe: poor, rural, and unskilled workers in sectors like steel, cement, and fertilisers face job losses, wage cuts, and heightened poverty, while richer urban groups are largely shielded. This evidence shows that macroeconomic assessments alone understate the risks: climate measures like CBAM, if not carefully managed, can deepen inequality in vulnerable countries. Tailored support and exemptions will therefore be essential to ensure that CBAM promotes global cooperation rather than exacerbates divides.

Policy recommendations

01.

Strengthen the **Social Climate Fund** for ETS 2.

The EU and Member States should reinforce the Social Climate Fund (SCF) as the main tool to offset the regressive impacts of ETS 2, with a focus on vulnerable households. Following the regulation, Member States should prioritise in their Social Climate Plans structural investments such as home renovation, affordable renewable heating, and affordable available public transport, as well as strengthened social protection systems, including adequate minimum income schemes, and avoid temporary income support that is not targeted to vulnerable households. By combining targeted short-term protection with long-term transformation, the SCF can prevent energy and transport poverty while enabling households to adapt to a low-carbon economy. To ensure adequacy, its budget should be expanded by pooling resources from both ETS and ETS 2 revenues and other national resources and managed with transparency to secure trust of people across Europe.

02.

Make CBAM a driver of **fairness and cooperation**.

CBAM should become a vehicle for climate solidarity and not framed as a mere trade instrument. At the EU level, support should be offered to SMEs through simplified reporting rules, technical assistance, and targeted financial help. Internationally, a portion of CBAM revenues should be allocated to assist developing countries via technology transfer, climate finance, and capacity building. This would align CBAM with principles of climate justice and reduce risks of trade tensions. By better embedding fairness at home and abroad, the mechanism can protect and support the EU industry while encouraging global convergence on climate action.

03.

Introduce **flexibility** and **exemptions** for the most vulnerable partners.

To strengthen CBAM's legitimacy and reduce risks of economic harm, the EU should adopt a differentiated approach in its application to partner economies. Critical subsectors with low emission intensity, as well as small-scale enterprises in low-income and vulnerable regions of the Global South, should be either exempted from CBAM or subject to reduced carbon tax rates. This would demonstrate the EU's commitment to the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and prevent disproportionate impacts on fragile economies. Coupled with transparent criteria for exemptions, such an approach would reinforce global trust, avoid retaliation, and enhance the EU's credibility as a leader in climate diplomacy.

04.

Build institutional and **technical capacity** in **trade partners**.

EU trading partners should strengthen their institutional and technical systems to better align with the EU's ambitious climate goals and avoid higher CBAM costs. This involves improving emissions data collection, developing transparent monitoring and reporting frameworks, and investing in skills and expertise to manage compliance effectively. By doing so, countries can reduce their vulnerability to CBAM charges and demonstrate progress toward low-carbon pathways. International partnerships, including technical and financial support from the EU, can facilitate this transition. Enhancing institutional and technical capacity will help trading partners integrate smoothly into global low-carbon markets while reinforcing the EU's push for a fair and ambitious climate agenda.

Policy recommendations

05.

Safeguard the integrity of the European Green Deal and **long-term climate ambition**.

The EU should avoid weakening core elements of the European Green Deal. Recent moves to introduce flexibilities in the 2040 climate target, roll back parts of the Common Agricultural Policy, water down the Nature Restoration Law, and ease corporate sustainability reporting risk undermining progress. Protecting these frameworks is essential to keep climate ambition on track, give people confidence in the transition, and uphold Europe's credibility as a global leader in climate action.

References & other info

● Cammeo, J., Ferrari, A., Borghesi, S., Zens, G., de Bonfils, L. (2024).
[*The functioning and socioeconomic impacts of the EU Emission Trading System: updated evidence and insights.*](#)
SPES Working paper no. 7.1, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios.
Florence: University of Florence.
Available at: <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables/>

● Cammeo, J., Ferrari, A., Borghesi, S., Dokken, T., (2025).
[*Understanding and assessing CBAM: vulnerability and impacts in the EU.*](#)
SPES Working Paper no. 7.2, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios.
Florence: University of Florence. Available at:
<https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables>

● Davalos, J., Henseler, M., Maisonnave, H., (2025).
[*The distributional effects of European climate policies in the Global South – a model-assessment for Egypt.*](#)
SPES Working Paper no. 7.3, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios.
Florence: University of Florence.
Available at: <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables>

● Salisu, A., A., Adediran, A., I. (2025)
[*A GVAR analysis of the macroeconomic effects of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism in the Global South.*](#)
SPES Focus - Work Package #7, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios.
Florence: University of Florence.
Available at: <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables>

This Policy Brief was written by

Jacopo Cammeo, European University Institute; Albert Ferrari, European University Institute.

Contributors and peer reviewers

Mario Biggeri, University of Florence; Simone Borghesi, European University Institute; Laura de Bonfils, Social Platform; Jorge Davalos, PEP - Partnership for Economic Policy; Therese Dokken, Oslo Metropolitan University; Andrea Ferrannini, University of Florence; Martin Henseler, PEP - Partnership for Economic Policy; Helene Maisonnaive, PEP - Partnership for Economic Policy; Afees Salisu, Centre for Econometrics and Applied Research; Idris Adediran, Centre for Econometrics and Applied Research; Katja Reuter, Social Platform.

Disclaimer

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

This document reflects the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Cover photo @Omkan Jadhav for Unsplash

Funded by European Union's Horizon
Europe Programme under Grant
Agreement No. 101094551

Sustainability
performances,
evidence & scenarios